

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF TRANSLATION OF
SOCIAL AND POLITICAL TEXTS

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Annotation: Along with lexical and grammatical transformations, stylistic transformations when translating socio-political texts are no less important.

The object of this study is socio-political texts.

The subject of the study was the genre and stylistic features of English-language texts with a socio-political orientation, as well as the ways of their transmission into Uzbek.

The practical significance of the study lies in the fact that the results of this work can be used in special courses on the problems of socio-political translation, and also aware of stylistics and general theory and practice of translation.

Keywords: socio-political text; genre-stylistic peculiarities; translation of the socio-political text; stylistic transformations.

Izoh: Leksik va grammatik o'zgarishlar bilan bir qatorda stilistik ijtimoiy-siyosiy matnlarni tarjima qilishda o'zgarishlar muhimlikda kam ahamiyatga ega emas.

Ushbu tadqiqot ob'ekti ijtimoiy-siyosiy matnlardir.

Ijtimoiy-siyosiy yo'nalishdagi ingliz tilidagi matnlarning janr va uslubiy xususiyatlari hamda ularni o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilish yo'llari tadqiqot mavzusi deb olindi.

Tadqiqotning amaliy ahamiyati shundan iboratki, bu ish natijalaridan ijtimoiy-siyosiy tarjima muammolari bo'yicha maxsus kurslarda foydalanish mumkin, shu bilan birga stilistika va tarjimaning umumiy nazariyasi va amaliyotida ham qo'llanilishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-siyosiy matn; janr-stilistik o'ziga xos xususiyatlar;

ijtimoiy-siyosiy matnni tarjima qilish; stilistik o'zgarishlar.

Аннотация: наряду с лексическими и грамматическими преобразованиями стилистические не менее важны при переводе общественно-политических текстов.

Объектом исследования являются общественно-политические тексты.

Предметом исследования стали жанровые и стилистические особенности англоязычных текстов общественно-политической направленности, а также способы их передачи на узбекский язык.

Практическая значимость исследования заключается в том, что результаты данной работы могут быть использованы в специальных курсах по проблемам общественно-политического перевода, а также знаком со стилистикой и общей теорией, и практикой перевода.

Ключевые слова: общественно-политический текст; жанрово-стилистические особенности; перевод общественно-политического текста; стилистические трансформации.

As a rule, the journalistic style combines alternation between expression and standard, constantly turning expressive means into a standard. According to Ya.I. Retzker, the task of the translator is to “transmit the content of the original holistically and accurately through another language, preserving its stylistic and expressive features” [6, p. 10].

The style of socio-political journalism is very close to the style of fiction.

When conveying stylistic features of English texts and socio-political orientation to the Uzbek language is necessary to keep in mind that not for each of them it is possible to select a full equivalent or partial match.

There is always a danger of not delivering the proper degree of emotional effect of the original or, conversely, unnecessarily embellish. To ensure greater adequacy of translation of the text, the translator should take into account the context, and style of the author, and also take into account the specifics of the target language.

The use of transformations helps to avoid translation errors.

Among the techniques that require stylistic transformations when translating into Uzbek or Russian are lexical repetitions, synonymous pairs, idioms, irony, metaphors, comparisons, and epithets.

As a practical part of our research, we used the texts from the INOSMI website. To analyze stylistic 287 features of the translation of texts on socio-political topics, we selected 27 stylistic units. Of these, 51.9% (13 units) were idioms and phraseological units, 11.1% each were epithets, metonymy, and metaphors (3 units each), and 7.4% (2 units each) were comparisons and lexical repetitions.

English socio-political texts include lexical repetitions and synonymous pairs much more often than Uzbek and Russian ones.

When translating, it is most often necessary to use omissions and substitutions. Sometimes the omission is partially compensated by using a synonymous pair.

However, this example shows that sometimes repetitions are left for emphasis: British business lost to European competitors. British entrepreneur crushed. British jobs were exported abroad. – British companies lost out to European competitors.

British entrepreneurs went bankrupt. British jobs have migrated to other countries [1]. The same rule applies to the translation of English idioms and expressive elements of the text.

In Uzbek language texts on socio-political topics for convictions, authors often resort to rhetorical pathos and a noble and solemn tone in conveying the text. It follows that socio-political texts are usually expressive. Fine expressive means (metaphors, comparisons, periphrases, etc.) are taken from the general language found in expressive means.

When conveying English idioms and other expressive elements into Uzbek or Russian, the ideal option would be to use similar combinations. However, the Uzbek or Russian idiom must correspond to the English one also stylistically: the

American way – to'laqonli amerikacha [2], cutting red tape – byurokratik kechikishlarni kamaytirish [1].

In socio-political texts, one can often notice figurative phraseology, with the help of which the author gives the statement expressiveness. According to V.N. Komissarov, figurative phraseological units, depending on the method of translation into Uzbek can be divided into four groups: phraseological units that have full correspondences in the Uzbek language (translation method: tracing), for example: space race – cosmic poyga[2]; phraseological units, the imagery of which is partially not coincides with Uzbek: goes back – orqaga ketadi [2]; phraseological units, the imagery of which does not coincide at all with Uzbek (translation method: complete replacement): to be spitting in the wind - vaqtni behuda sarflash[2]; phraseological units requiring neutral translation: wrappings economic initiatives firmly in the flag - iqtisodiy tashabbuslar yordamida o'z vatanparvarligingizni namoyish eting [2], [5].

The use of stylistic replacement techniques can be considered in specific examples:

- 1) replacing verb forms in English headings with nominal forms during translation: Florida Air Force base for top stealth fighter-jet stakes a 'direct hit' from Hurricane Michael – "Maykl" to'foni: "to'g'ridan-to'g'ri zarba" Floridadagi AQSh Havo kuchlarining eng yaxshi yashirin qiruvchilarining bazasi [4];
- 2) replacing colloquial elements of slang and familiar nature with more neutral ones: money-loser is an unprofitable measure- foyda keltirmaydigan chora [2].
- 3) a loose requirement for brevity in Uzbek newspaper materials: Wait, there's more. There's a reason Biden's people put "made in America" in the title of their tax plan. - But wait, wait, we have something else. There's a reason why Biden's supporters used the phrase "made in America" in the title of his tax plan [2].

Headlines play an important role in journalistic texts, the main function of which, in addition to being informative, is to attract the reader's attention. To do

this, in headings, as a rule, articles and personal forms of the auxiliary verb “To be” are omitted, and the action is expressed in Indefinite or Continuous forms: The bill for Boris Johnson’s Brexit is coming in and it’s punishingly steep – (meaning) Boris Brexit Johnson’s bill is already in force, and it is extremely harsh [1].

To approximate an event that happened recently, use the form Present Indefinite, for the future - an infinitive, and to add emotionality, neologisms are interspersed into the common vocabulary, dialectisms, or slang, for example:

Bidenomics is as American as Apple Pie – Bidenomics: this is purely in the American spirit [2]. Also, the headings of socio-political texts are characterized by the use of abbreviations: ‘World’s First’ Animal Covid-19 Vaccine Registered in Russia – Here’s What That Means – “The world’s first” registered in Russia covid-19 vaccine for animals [3].

In Uzbek and Russian newspaper texts, unlike English ones, authors often resort to a high tone of text transmission. This excludes the use of abbreviations for the names and surnames of famous personalities. In American and English newspapers may use familiar words, from the point of view of Russian newspaper style, to appeal to politicians. For their transmission, the translator is forced to resort to stylistic adaptation: abbreviated names are translated into Russian using substitutions: Teddy Roosevelt – Theodore Roosevelt, F.D.R. – Franklin Delano Roosevelt [2].

To summarize, we can note that socio-political texts are characterized by several stylistic features that cause difficulties in the translation process, since adequate translation of a socio-political text, in addition to the factually accurate rendering of the content, must convey to the reader all the emotional elements contained in the original. It should also be noted that figurative means such as metaphors, idioms, metonymies, and comparisons, as a rule, are transmitted into Uzbek and Russian using full or partial equivalents. The translator's goal is to ensure that the translated newspaper text has the same impact on the reader as the original. However, the analysis of the translation confirmed that the translator’s use

of full and partial substitutions is quite large, which determines the fact that when conveying stylistic features, the imagery of the translation text does not always correspond to the imagery of the original text.

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